

Mapping Dancer's Movements Onto a Robotic Arm, a PCA-based Approach

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Abstract—Robotics and dance share the study of movement as an investigation field for pragmatic and aesthetic purposes, respectively. In this work, we propose a principal component analysis (PCA) based method to create robot-augmented choreographies projecting human dancing movements onto robotic arm ones. Our results will not only impacts on the discipline of dance but also on the research topic of embodiment of non-anthropomorphic avatars in the real and virtual world.

Index Terms—Art and Entertainment Robotics, Motion Planning Human-Robot Mapping

I. INTRODUCTION

Research in anthropological and neuroaesthetics has investigated the perception of dancing movements, identifying kinematic parameters like amplitude and variability that affect the audience aesthetic experience [1], [2]. Several research teams have designed strategies and policies to project human dancing movements onto humanoid robots [3], creating also human-robot choreography as the Waltz performance presented in [4]. Although the significant advancement of robotic dance [5], most of the investigations have been focused on humanoid robots. Therefore, leveraging our expertise on human-onto-robot projection [6], [7] we propose a strategy for mapping dancing movements onto robot with dissimilar kinematics respect to the human as robot manipulator.

II. MOTION MAPPING

The main challenge of the proposed consists in the abundant degrees of freedom (DoFs) observed in human movements to map onto the limited DoFs of a robot manipulator. To address this challenge, we use Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to identify the most significant human joints involved in the performance and then establish a one-to-one mapping between these selected human joints and the robot ones. To do this, firstly, we define the instantaneous contribution of i -th joint to the motion $\theta_{h|i}(t)$ is evaluated as norm of its pose $q_{h|i}(t)$:

$$\theta_{h|i} = \|q_{h|i}\|_2 = \sqrt{\alpha_{h|i}^2 + \beta_{h|i}^2 + \gamma_{h|i}^2} \quad \forall i \in [1, N] \quad (1)$$

with N the number of monitored joints of the human body at the time instant t and $\alpha_{h|i}, \beta_{h|i}, \gamma_{h|i}$ the elementary rotations around the three main axes. Once defined the joint contribution, the mapping approach follows four main steps (Fig. 1):

s.1 - A principal components analysis is conducted on human joint contribution time series to evaluate the first

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of proposed mapping method.

significant principal component (PC) of dancer movements and the contribution of each i -th joint to this, v_i .

s.2 - The human body is then divided in half along the transverse plane and the joints are grouped into two subsets (I_r and I_l). The right subset I_r collects joints in the right half body of the dancer while the left one I_l contains the joints in the left part. Each subset shares the joints of the spine.

s.3 - The maximum sub-subsets contributions to the motion, z_r and z_l , are evaluated as the expressive capabilities of the original human movements space using k joint, with k the number of DoFs of the mapping target manipulator:

$$z_\epsilon = \max \left\{ \sum_{i \in \tilde{I}_\epsilon} |v_i| \right\} \quad \forall \epsilon \in \{r, l\} \quad (2)$$

Then we extrapolate the most involved joints set \hat{I} as:

$$\hat{I} = \begin{cases} \arg \max_{\tilde{I}_r} \left\{ \sum_{i \in \tilde{I}_r} |v_i| \right\} & \text{if } z_r > z_l \\ \arg \max_{\tilde{I}_l} \left\{ \sum_{i \in \tilde{I}_l} |v_i| \right\} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

s.4 - Once identified the half body most involved in the choreography and the \hat{I} sub-subset of joints that meet the maximum condition in Eq. (3), the movement of human joints is then mapped in the space joints of the robotic manipulator. Among all the possible allocation of i -th human joint onto j -th robotic one, three sorting strategies have been investigated:

- Decreasing order based on valence (**DVo**), the more a human joint contributes to the choreography the more the robotic joint in which it is mapped is close to the base of the manipulator.

	q_r				
DVo	$\theta_{h 21}$	$\theta_{h 20}$	$\theta_{h 19}$	$\theta_{h 13}$	$\theta_{h 12}$
IVo	$\theta_{h 12}$	$\theta_{h 13}$	$\theta_{h 19}$	$\theta_{h 20}$	$\theta_{h 21}$
HSo	$\theta_{h 21}$	$\theta_{h 20}$	$\theta_{h 19}$	$\theta_{h 12}$	$\theta_{h 13}$

TABLE I: Summary of three different joint assignments from the human body to the robotic arm.

- Increasing order based on valence (**IVo**), the more a human joint contributes to the dance the more the robotic joint in which it is mapped is close to the end-effector.
- Increasing human skeleton order (**HSo**), the closer the human joint is to the feet, the closer the robotic joint in which is mapped to the base.

The joint contribution is estimated as the percentage of movement reconstructed by only that joint rotation enabling only the first PC.

III. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

We conducted a user study to assess the effectiveness of aesthetic movement mapping and to compare various ordering policies regarding audience perception. The survey was submitted and completed by ten participants (5 female, 4 male, and 1 non-binary). Each participant observed twelve distinct human-robot fragments of hip-hop choreographies (the dance style was chosen together with a professional dancer to stress the proposed mapping algorithm). The professional dancer wore an IMU-based suit to collect joint trajectory and then three human-robot choreography, once per ordering policies, are simulated in a virtual environment. The virtual scene consisted of a human mannequin alongside a virtual representation of a Kinova Mico 2 robot arm (Kinova Inc., QB). The human mannequin reproduced the dancer’s movements, while the robot arm served as a test platform for evaluating the mapping method and the ordering policies. Given the choreography and collected data, the results of the assignments are presented in Tab. I. The submitted survey was composed of nine Likert scale items, each with 8 levels, to assess perceived beauty (**Be**), elegance (**El**), attractiveness (**At**), likeness (**Li**) of the choreography, balance (**Ba**), movement beauty (**MoBe**), human-likeness (**HuLi**), integration (**In**), and full-body motion (**FuBo**).

The collected opinions on these aesthetic items violated the assumption of normality according to the results of the Jarque-Bera test ($p < 0.05$), consequently was conducted the statistical comparison by the Kruskal-Wallis test, which returned a statistical difference for At $p = 0.028$, El $p = 0.040$, Li $p = 0.023$, Ba $p = 0.03$, MoBe $p = 0.0164$ and HuLi $p = 0.0137$. The post hoc analysis with a Bonferroni adjustment revealed that the statistical difference exists exclusively between the inspired human assignment method, HSo, and the increasing assignment based on valence, IVo. In more detail, the inspired human skeleton order positively impacts the aesthetic perception of the choreography and movement of the robot according to the metrics of *i*) El +4.89 %, *ii*) At +4.69 %, *iii*) Li +4.87 %, *iv*) Ba +4.69 %, *v*) MoBe +4.73 %, and *vi*) HuLi +4.68 %. The

Fig. 2: Results based on the collected participant opinions.

no statistical difference between DVo and HSo methods may be due to the similarity of the two policies. In general, a high level of approval (> 5) is reached by all policies.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this research, we have designed a novel approach to create human-robot choreographies projecting human aesthetic expression onto a dissimilar kinematic chain as a robotic manipulator. The mapping method starts with analyzing the dancer’s primary movements by means of a PCA, identifying the most crucial joints predominantly involved in the choreography from the more variable half-body subset. These joint configurations are then mapped one-to-one onto a robotic arm imposing several strategies for ordering. To determine the most effective joint ordering from human to robot, we collected and analyzed the feedback from ten participants on their aesthetic perception evaluated by nine items. In the future steps of our study, we will compare the effects on different choreographies and experiment with diverse kinematic structures.

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